

20M1258 REFLECTIVE PAPER

BM5102 – ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR
MASTER IN MANAGEMENT BY COURSEWORK
SCHOOLS OF BUSIENSS AND ECONOMICS
UNIVERSITI OF BRUNEI DARUSSALAM

Before Experience

Starting the master program in August 2020 seems like a wrong timing due to COVID-19 pandemic which changes the way how the course works. Most of the modules had to remove exam from the module course and emphasize more such as on report assignment, quiz and presentation. However, no one is to blame here as the reason for doing all that is just to comply with the safety guidelines recommended by Brunei's Ministry of Health due to the unexpected situation. Despite the unfamiliarity, I believe that as a future manager, I shouldn't be complaining about the situations that are not under my control, and I only need to adapt and control whatever I can. I am still optimistic that I can learn a lot especially in the first semester where I'm taking five modules altogether and honestly not disappointed with the new useful information and skills I received. Especially through module Organisational behaviour, I believe the highlight of taking this module is that I have significantly improved my report writing skills as I am very unfamiliar with it because of my major is in Mathematics and we don't do report writing. We were given two report writing assignments, one of it is individual reports while the other one is group reports.

For individual reports, my first plan is to study how internal communication can help to create an emotional culture in corporate organisations, inspired by Men and Yue (2019) study. Their findings mentioned that positive emotional culture among the employees can be created through symmetrical internal communication and responsive leadership communications. They also found that when there is a positive emotional environment, the employee would advocate more towards their organisation. I find this topic is very interesting as I believe whatever findings I get; it would be useful for my future career as communication is very important in every organisation. I read a lot regarding the topic "Communication" along the way and have found various studies regarding the topic. I have to be honest that at first, I couldn't able to comprehend how the information is portrayed in the first five or six articles I've read as I'm not familiar with reading articles. I also not familiar with all the website for reliable sources such as Scopus, ScienceDirect and Emerald and thankfully my lecturer gives some tips on how to properly find relevant articles. I do not like it at first but as time goes by, I'm slowly able to grasp how to understand the articles and start to enjoying articles.

My next struggle is to write the research proposal to be submitted. I have been trying to avoid writing since I was in my sixth form as I am not good with expressing especially in English. It was a mistake of me to do that in the past and because of it, I am struggling with how to properly plan for my reports. I guess at that time I am a short-minded person but it changed after my discovery year as I'm having both as internship and I believe that I have more to learn and thus I have decided to take Master in Management. My biggest weakness in writing the research proposal is how I can connect what I want to study with the findings from various articles and what is the limit for me to give my opinion for my research. I honestly have no ideas on how to write the literature review part and I believe my proposals are not up to the standard of master students. I am happy however that I have friends taking the same master program they have been very helpful towards me when I am in difficulty. They can pinpoint what are my mistakes and suggestions on some of the tips and tricks which I believe would make it easier for me. As we are required to submit our proposal for ethics form, I also struggle with creating the survey to be used for my research. I'm surprised that all research articles studied do not include their research questions and since I'm not sure how I just make my questions myself based on the literature review. However, as I'm still learning at that time and looking at it now, I believe I can do my proposal way better than that.

For the group assignment, we were given the task to find out what is the issues and challenges for a multinational company in Brunei and I was in a group with my friend other two students. I have to mention that due to the COVID-19 situation; it is not easy to do the work in groups as we are not from same tutorial class and most of the time, we discuss through Zoom call or WhatsApp. However, I am thankful towards my groupmates as they know what to do especially Izzati because at that time I'm still clueless on what to do. We discussed what cultural models we can use and which company would be our focus of study. Surprisingly it is quite hard to get for the company willing to cooperate with the research and probably due to they couldn't fully understand what we are trying to study and might think it is unnecessary especially in this situation. We only able to get one or two companies out of ten planned and thus we have to change instead of collecting the issues and challenges from different companies, we have just to focus on one and discuss it further.

However due to unforeseen circumstances, we have to change both individual report and group reports instead of using primary data, we have to use secondary data. This does take a toll on our mental because the due date is nearing and we have to be quick to decide what are we going to do. For my report, as I have read a lot regarding communication, I have decided to do a systematic literature review on the impact of internal communication satisfaction. While for the group report, we have an emergency discussion through Google Meet on what are we going to do and then we come to a conclusion to change our group report into an impactful project report, with the topic is regarding about the mental health of nurses during this pandemic and thankfully for our lecturer to approve and supporting us for this project.

During experience

Firstly, the focus is on the group project as the due date is nearer. We start the research by creating the research questions first so that we can know what is our focus for the finding parts. Me and groupmates then together we decided to split websites so that we can get as many articles from different sources. We are comparing how different countries have a different approach to help to reduce the nurses' mental burden as due to the pandemic, nurse's mental health is heavily affected by it. Then we're finding out what are the common impacts of COVID-19 and then we also compile what are the suggestions and approached taken from different countries so that we compare and pick which we redeemed as the best approach to be taken to help with this issue. The main challenges during the process of finding the article, there are not many articles published yet because COVID-19 is a new issue and we believe it takes time for a researcher to conduct their studies. After several days of looking for resources, then we together plan on how the structure of our paper would be and once everyone satisfied, we proceed with writing the paper.

Then all of us prepared the introduction part and then combined all articles we have found into two tables, one for the impact and one for the suggestion or approach is taken. Once we created the table, we then list down on each article what is the impact of COVID-19 on the nurses' mental health and have found that psychological stress & distress, anxiety and depression as the common impacts. We also list downs what are the suggestion or approach taken from the same articles at previous tables and once that part is done, we proceed with our findings. As one member have to withdraw from the program, we split the finding part into three categories. First is discussing how the mental health of nurses can be affected. The second part would be what are the common impacts and thirdly is the suggestion and approach taken and then our suggestion. We pick which part we would like to prepare and I have chosen the third part of the discussion. Many of the

suggestions emphasizing the priority to make sure the mental health of nurses stable and this is are to be expected as their jobs are already in a stressful environment, then come COVID-19 which make things worse for them. I have learned that organisational, leader and public support are very crucial so that they are not demotivated at their works. Some of the suggestion and approach have taken also mentioned to be flexible with the nurses such as in terms of schedule as rigid schedule may not be favourable by them. Although the suggestions and approach taken are specifically for the nurses', I also can relate it if I become a manager in the future. It is undeniable that the mental health of employee must be properly taken and do not put too much pressure which is not beneficial not only for the employee but also for the organisations. Thus, it's a reminder for me to not exhaust the mental health not only of my staff but also for myself. Once we've done the discussion part, we conclude our findings and then proceed with preparing the teaching note. I believe the teaching note is the best way to summarise our reports and at the same time still keeping the valuable information. Once everything is done, we check our report again for any mistake and submitted it after satisfy with it.

With the group assignment submitted, I then can put my focus on my individual analysis report. Since there is not much time left and I already changed my topic, my lecturer had requested for me to submit to her my report progress plan timeline and I find it very helpful as it helps me to stay aware with the due date. I also felt like changing the topic is my second chance to make my report arrangement, wording and content better than the first one I have submitted before. First is that I have to find as many articles I can and even analyse and understand it as fast I can. I've created a table in Microsoft Excel where I put the key details from every article and its link and by doing this, it helps me to easily refer back to all articles. Before writing out the report, I have read the systematic review articles send by my lecturer and once again very thankful for it as it helps me to give some ideas on how I should structure my report. I find that once I have my structure, then it would be easier for me to proceed with the report. After doing several report assignments from this module and other modules, I have found out that I am very weak with the introduction parts as it is hard for me to think of how to start and what I should include in it. I have to read different articles to find out how they prepare their introduction and I got several ideas on it but still are not that confident with it.

Once my introduction part finished, then I proceed to prepare for my finding. I organise my findings based on the example given and I use the same method as in the group reports for my individual analysis report. I organise it based on the number of articles from each country so that I can find out which country has studied the most regarding the impact of internal communication satisfaction and which dimensions they find important. Regarding the dimensions, I have found two communication satisfaction survey which is one by Downs and Hazen in 1977 and Hertz 1978 and have decided to pick articles mainly using Downs and Hazen survey. They have eight dimensions altogether which include the general organisational perspective, organisational integration, personal feedback, relation with supervisor, relation with subordinates, horizontal-informal communication, media quality and the communication climate (Downs & Hazen, 1997). As I narrow down my focus, obviously my choices become limited and thus I did include some of the articles which also mentioned some of the dimensions despite not using the survey model. Reason for it is that they are still related to the dimensions and provide interesting findings too.

The difference between this and the one with the group report is that now I have to do it alone and it is quite difficult as there are many articles I have to filter out. Nevertheless, it still a valuable experience for me and quite proud that I can achieve this by myself.

Then when it comes to organising the information for discussion, I have to be honest that I am very frustrated with it as when doing it, I do realize that there is some mistake at the finding part and so I have to change and recheck everything. I believe it is due to me pushing myself to catch up with the deadline and so I have made some of the mistakes which can be avoided in the first place. I also have to filter again few articles as I couldn't connect their points with what I'm doing at that time and have to adjust the finding part again. Despite that, I able to discuss my research questions based on my findings and I found that relationship with the supervisor as the most important dimensions for internal communication satisfaction. I also found that when an employee is satisfied with their internal communication, there is also a relation with job satisfaction and it has been mentioned at least in one article from six different countries which confirmed the finding which mentioned that there is positive relation in between communication satisfaction and job satisfaction (Downs, 1988 as cited in Pongton & Suntrayuth, 2019). So, based on my findings, there is another additional input for my future career where the manager needs to take care of the relationship with their staff and must make sure that there is a quality communication as it has a various impact towards the organisations and employees. Once I'm satisfied with the discussion, I proceed with my limitations and conclusion and organising the reference part. Before submitting, I recheck my report several times and only submit it once I'm happy with it.

Completion experience

Overall, I do believe that for both group and individual reports I have achieved my research target. Through both assignments, I have learned many kinds of stuff along the way whether academically or personal skills. Academically, I have learned to take care of the mental health of health, to communicate properly and to take care of the relationship with either peers or staffs. I have come across with many new terms and concepts which I believe would be useful to be used practically in the future. In terms of skills, I believe that my reports writing skills have been improving drastically compared to before taking this master program. I also enjoyed reading findings by other researchers and I do find the fun part of being a researcher. For the group reports, what I have learned which is very important is that it is necessary to delegate the task as it would make the task easier. Communication is important also so that we know the progress of each other and seek recommendations when we are having some difficulty with our own task.

However, despite my report writing skills have been improving, I do believe that it is still not up to the standard of a master student. There is one comment regarding my individual report where the commentator mentioned that he/she confused with my citations and after checking my report again I felt disappointed that there are a couple of mistakes which should not be there in the first place. I also disappointed with myself that I'm still poor with my time management time because some of the time I am distracted instead of focusing on my report. In summary, I believe that I have more to be improved personally if I want to become a proper manager in the future. There is a finding which mentioned that employers believed that the youth are lacking in terms of

self-awareness, wisdom and leadership capability and thus I believed that I need to improve on those mention criteria (Musa & Idris, 2020).

As now I have some experience with writing reports, I believe I can improve on some of my weakness and mistakes from previous reports. First, I should improve self-discipline on time management as it is the key to finish my task on time because with good time management would reduce frustration, increased productivity and sharpens my techniques and skills (Kenneth, 2012). Second is that I should read more articles than usual as reading can help me to study and widen my thinking based on how they write their reports and findings. thirdly is to allocate a big task into several small parts as this way would be easier to be done. Fourth, for group works it is important to divide task fairly and to always communicate so that we stay on track.

Finally, I believe that this reflective report helps me to realise my strength, weakness, mistake and success during the one-semester with this module. As noted by Musa and Idris (2020) that self-awareness is an important aspect which would be looked at by the employer's and this reflective report allow me to be better at self-aware. I end this reflective report with very thankful remarks for my lecturer who have been guiding and helping us along with the module progress. I remembered at first, I almost give-up due to the immense pressure but when I change my mindset, the path had become clearer and finally enjoyed with all I have been doing.

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